

Photovoltaic Solar Thermal (PV/T) Collectors Past, Present and Future: A Review

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Abstract

Every day more research is made in the field of solar energy specifically in hybrid photovoltaic/thermal (PV/T) collectors, which is a combination of both solar technologies. Researchers have targeted this system configuration because it has an improved overall efficiency, with a comparison to both photovoltaic (PV) and solar collectors, and it saves space using one area for two systems instead of using two zones. The majority of researchers presented new models/designs while others provide studies on pre-existing ones for different environmental conditions. However, it is important to review their work to find key ideas to consider for future works and to capture the limitations of research in this field. This paper presents principles of PV/T collectors, classification, history of research, major aspects in PV/T research and critical review of the presented review literature, as well as the PV aspect of the system. More focus in this study is directed towards the electrical side, in particular, the PV part of the system.

Keywords: Review Hybrid PV/T collectors; Photovoltaics; Solar thermal collectors.

INTRODUCTION

The global demand for energy have increased with the increasing population and resources like fossil fuels are not reliable as it was in the previous century, as fluctuation in oil prices can be very damaging especially to countries and industries that consider fossil fuel as their base. Renewable energy technologies have become main stream during the last three decades; treaties set by decision makers were signed to establish renewable energy as a global solution to problems such as energy shortage and global warming. Solar power is one of the leading renewable energy resources due to its low price for individuals and it emitting zero emissions and noise. Two major technologies used under the solar power umbrella are the solar cell 'Photovoltaic' and the solar thermal collector.

The first one converts sunlight into electrical energy while the later heats fluids using the sunlight's heat to create thermal energy. Both techniques utilize the solar energy; however, each method covers a particular part of the spectrum; photovoltaic (PV) covers the visible spectrum while solar thermal collector covers the rest. A notion of emerging both techniques into one unit has been suggested to create -what is known as – Photovoltaic Solar Thermal Collector (PV/T).

The PV/T technology capitalizes on the entire spectrum to generate both electrical and thermal energy in the same space. Efficiency is higher in this combined system in comparison to separate PV and Solar thermal conventional systems. This mainly due to the common denominator of these two systems, which is temperature? PV cell's efficiency decrease with the increasing temperature of the cell, this is no longer a problem because of the coupled solar thermal collector. The fluid in the collector (could be Air, Water, etc.) will absorb the heat of the PV cell/module, and so output voltage of the PV cell can be maintained. On the other hand, the fluid is now heated and ready to be used for various applications.

Many studies are conducted in this branch of solar energy, as it hovers over a long list of techniques which leads to more combinations. The PV technology could be made with different silicon material, set up to a different configuration and installed in various environments. Same can be said about the solar thermal collector. In order to understand and grasp on the PV/T technology a deeper research on each aspect (PV and Thermal) must be made.

Researchers have not necessarily raised the system as a whole, but rather focused on a certain parameter to improve or conducted a case study. This paper aims to revise and review the PV/T technology and take a look at its two entities separately as well in order to draw conclusions. More than 65 research paper published over a range of journals and conferences are being discussed and will be presented to establish main points, general trends, and problems to be solved in relation to this topic.

PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF PV/T:

A. The PV/T collector system is formed of two subsystems:

1. Solar Thermal Collectors: A device that utilizes on the solar radiation (ultraviolet and infrared) to heat up a fluid with good heat capacity to create thermal energy. This fluid may be used to heat water through a heat exchanger system. The overall system is used to supply hot water for residential applications; however, it can be used to produce electricity by coupling the system with a turbine. The fluid used in the thermal collector can be air, water or other liquid material. Many configurations and designs of a solar thermal collector are present such as parabolic trough collectors, batch box heated, concentrated solar power, etc. To ensure the production of high temperatures for these fluids, the tubes carrying them are colored with black to absorb more radiation and heat up the liquid [1]-[2].
2. Photovoltaic or solar cells: A device that converts light (photons) into electricity in the form of a direct current. These devices are of semiconductor materials, utilizing the energy the photons give to the electrons in the valence band and raising them to the conduction band which leads to creating an electron-hole pair. Capitalizing on this pair through the use of a potential barrier to create a potential difference (Voltage) is important. Finally, an external circuit with a load is connected to this device to create current flow. The simplest element is the solar cell, and usually, PV's are sold as either PV Modules or

PV Panels (modules are made up of cells and panels are made up of modules) [2]-[3].

3. PV/T: The hybrid solar thermal collector produces both electricity and thermal energy simultaneously due to using both PV and Thermal collectors. Many configurations of this system are examined to provide higher overall efficiency. The efficiency of the PV/T system is calculating by adding the electrical efficiency to the thermal one. Advantages of this system are summarized below [4]-[5]:
 - i. PV/T system uses up less area than PV and Thermal collectors separately.
 - ii. PV/T system requires less material than fixing two individual systems.
 - iii. Electrical efficiency can be improved due to the fluid absorbing heat from the PV.
 - iv. Fluid gaining more temperature due to the heat it absorbs from the solar cell.
 - v. Higher overall efficiency than separate systems.

B. Classification of PV/T

Classification of PV/T is crucial to simplify and ease the process of studying its types independently or grouped, compare different types and in the case of similarity combine them under one classification. It depends on multiple parameters, such as the nature of the heat transfer fluid in the system, the type of the collector used, etc. Figure 1 presents general PV/T classification [6]-[9].

A different classification can be proposed such that it also depends on the type of PV module or its configuration (stand-alone/grid-tie).

Figure 1: Classification of PV/T collector systems

PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE WORK OF PV/T:

A. Past Work:

Table 1 represents merely samples of past work done on this topic over the last four decades for different purposes such as design, theoretical study and case studies. The mentioned

articles show the importance of PV/T research and the scale it carries over multiple dimensions. The sample is insignificant to give a clear impression on the previous trend indeed, but common features can still be taken and compared with other work in that time scale to develop a clearer understanding of

the literature perhaps. The following points must be taken into consideration:

- 1) Most of the research present in the table uses both theoretical analysis and experimental data and compares the two.

- 2) More numerical simulation is established from the 80's to the present date than the 70's.

- 3) More focus on the type of collector used in PV/T was carried from 90's to present time.

Table 1. Conducted research over four decades with two samples of research per decade

Decade	Year	Ref.	Authors	Work
70's	1978	[39]	Kern E. & Russell M.	Performed tests & studies on the combined PV/T collector system and setup a full-system experiment.
	1979	[40]	Florschuetz L.	Provided a modification to the original Hottel-Whilier model for thermal analysis of flat-plate collectors to extend to the hybrid PV/T design.
80's	1980	[41]	Hendrie S.	Tested the performance of two PV/T types (Air & liquid type) of collectors through experiment and analytical prediction. Author recommended the careful choice of cover-glass spacing turbulent flow inducement in transfer fluid.
	1985	[42]	Cox H. & Raghuraman P.	Used a computer simulation of PV/T that applies to different designs to discuss important parameters for PV/T optimization. Authors focused on Air-type PV/T collector with a single crystalline PV.
90's	1994	[43]	Garg H. et al.	Presented an experimental study and compared it to a theoretical one for hybrid PV/T Solar water heater. Authors chose a thermosiphon water heat with solar cells. Experimental data validated theoretical predictions.
	1999	[44]	Garg H. et al.	Theoretically analyzed the performance of PV/T air heating collector with Compound Parabolic Concentrator (CPC) troughs. Authors conducted a comparison between PV/T system with and without CPC. Concluded that PV/T system with CPC has higher performance than without.
2000's	2000	[45]	Sopian K. et al.	Developed & tested a double pass PV/T type collector and applied it for solar drying. Authors performed both theoretical & experimental studies with results being in agreement and recommended the use of double pass PV/T for such application.
	2002	[46]	Zondag H. et al.	Presented four numerical models to simulate thermal output of PV/T collector. Results from these models are compared with experimental ones. A 5% accuracy to the experiment results is reached by all models.

B. Present Work:

B.1 PV/T General Aspect:

The following literature shows several researches in the field of PV/T; it is important to understand different scientific approaches to enhance experience and understanding of the core principles of this area.

Sopian *et al.* [1] examined the effects of bifacial air based Photovoltaic Thermal collector (PV/T) under the first law of thermodynamics. The authors designed four bifacial modules consisting of two path types which are a single path and a

double path parallel flow. The study found that the two parallel paths have the best efficiency around 45 to 64 %.

Fudholi *et al.* [2] used energy and exergy analysis to rate the effect of spiral flow absorber on a water based PV/T panel's efficiency and found a maximum PV/T efficiency of 68% and a PV efficiency of 13-13.8%. Furthermore, the authors concluded that the primary energy-saving efficiency had increased from 79% to 91% when mass flow rate increased from 0.011 kg/s to 0.041 kg/s.

Sopian *et al.* [3] compared three different collectors (serpentine flow absorber, oscillatory flow absorber, and parallel-serpentine flow absorber) regarding their PV/T efficiency and primary energy saving efficiency to determine their performance on a Building Integrated PV/T (BIPVT) to decide which has the best characteristics. Authors found that parallel-serpentine flow absorber gave the highest efficiency at a mass flow rate of 0.041 kg/s with a PV/T efficiency of 65% and a PV efficiency of 13%. Authors also concluded that mass flow rate is directly proportional to PV/T and Primary energy saving efficiencies.

Staebler *et al.* [4] proposed using transparent PV modules to replace the cover glass in glazed thermal collectors. The PV was of amorphous silicon, and that is because of its relatively low cost which could be suitable for BIPV systems. The study found a final PV/T efficiency of 32.5% with 4.7% being PV efficiency.

Jian and Mingheng [5] performed a study and numerical simulation on a solar concentrating PV/T to see whether they would improve the effectiveness or not. The system is single-

Lv *et al.* [9] authors analyzed thermoelectric properties of a PV/T module through indoors testing using a solar simulator. They used a monocrystalline silicon PV cell with a tilt angle of 20° and through a numerical study; they found a PV efficiency of 10.1 % and a PV/T efficiency of 54.3%.

Hajji *et al.* [10] proposed a numerical module of PV/T collector through MATLAB software. This module was based on energy balance equations to allow finding different temperature profile across PV/T layers. The PV cell used is of monocrystalline silicon type, and the tube and sheet collector type was chosen. Authors compared various mass flow rates to corresponding cell temperatures and found that the relationship between mass flow rate and cell temperature is inversely proportional.

Ammous and Chaabene [8] discussed using PV/T in powering a Reverse Osmosis (RO) standalone desalination plant and ran a simulation. Authors found electrical and thermal efficiencies of 18% and 68%, respectively. Leading to a PV/T efficiency that exceeds 75%. They also found that thermal energy peaks at 910 W/m² around 12 o'clock at noon, while electrical power peaks around 180 W/m² at the same time.

Haddad *et al.* [11] compared between PV/T system and separate PV and thermal systems to investigate the effectiveness of this technique. The authors used a monocrystalline silicon PV module with copper tubes, as they have set up three systems (conventional PV, conventional thermal and PV/T hybrid). Authors found a thermal efficiency of 42% at 12 o'clock noon. However, authors did not further discuss the effectiveness of the neither PV/T nor contemporary readings for the electrical performance of the system.

Athukorala *et al.* [12] introduced a techno-economic analysis for BIPVT system with few case studies to evaluate the role of

pass with three trough concentrators and fins. This study focused on factors affecting temperature. They concluded that the thermal and electrical efficiencies of the system are higher with Compound Parabolic Concentrators than without it.

Touafek *et al.* [6] presented a new configuration of hybrid PV/T using a monocrystalline silicon PV module, heat exchanger, new hybrid sensor, and tube and sheet absorber type and through the use of data acquisition system authors drew the temperature plots. The study concluded that the effectiveness of this design as well as the effect of temperature on the system output.

Croitoru [7] presented a review of PV/T combi-panels and their classifications. The survey showed different types of panel designs (uncovered panels, dual-flow panels, and two-phase panels) and classified combi-panels into PV/T water collector, combination water/Air PV/T collector, PV/T air collector – single pass and PV/T Air collector – double pass. The author showed the advantages and disadvantages of each type as well as named different technologies of each of them.

PV/T in this system. The author used the Life Cycle Cost (LCC) equations for cost analysis. PV used is of polycrystalline silicon type. Finally, authors concluded that increase in solar panel capacity results in a decrease in grid interaction and LCC of the system.

Khelifa *et al.* [13] provided an approach to model PV/T collector through the use of theoretical and experimental results, using energy balance equations and coupled differential equations. The authors performed a heat balance equation to all elements of the system (glass cover, PV, Coolant, Absorber plate and Insulation). The PV/T efficiency found was 69% (which is composed of 14.8% PV and 55% Thermal). The study proposed using advantage material to reduce costs.

Ammous *et al.* [14] proposed using a Fuzzy Logic Control (FLC) to employ a PV/T in RO desalination plant. The authors used Tube and sheet collector type and showed that conventional PV temperature is way higher than that of hybrid PV/T. However, the authors did not present the system efficiency or an economic study of it.

Hajji *et al.* [15] performed a comparison between two PV/T models: The first model (A) uses a tube and sheet collector. The second model (B) was a hybrid air/water collector. Both models use a monocrystalline silicon photovoltaic. Authors designed a numerical model via MATLAB to find the different temperature layers of PV/T collectors. Model A presented higher electrical efficiency with 13.8 % at 0.06 kg/s flow rate, while model B's efficiency was 11% at the same flow rate.

Reatti *et al.* [16] proposed an analytical expression to compare the produced energy by a concentrator PV/T module to the distance between subsequent collectors. Besides, a comparison between actual plant production and expected energy production was made. This study was achieved through the help of a monitoring system which acquires

various data such as (Temperature, mass flow rate, current, direct & global solar radiations, wind speed & direction, pressure and humidity).

Slimani *et al.* [17] studied effects of adding a cover glass & a metal plate on improving heat transfer & energy performance of PV/T. The PV module chosen for this design is a monocrystalline silicon cell. The PV efficiency has decreased due to this design from 11% to 9.5%, but the thermal efficiency was increased from 15% to 70%. The authors concluded that even though the PV efficiency has decreased, the overall PV/T efficiency of this particular design is very promising.

Marimuthu *et al.* [18] proposed a new PV/T water system with a transparent photovoltaic panel to replace non-transparent cell panels. AUTOCAD and MATLAB SIMULINK software was used to design and fabricate the experimental setup. It was found that the efficiency of the PV/T system increased under this design.

Haber [19] applied a metal absorber & collector tube to the back face of a conventional PV module and an insulated backside. The author created a heat transfer matrix for the analysis of this system and found that a PV/T with heat control and a PV/T without cooling have yearly efficiencies of 14.46% and 14.61%, respectively.

Haiping *et al.* [20] designed a CPC-PV/T system with light distribution uniformly found via Light tools simulation (numerical). Authors recommended using non-cover, water-cooled, flat cartridge collectors with three flow ducts (fins). The authors installed two CPC-PV/T units for this experiment and found a PV/T efficiency of 60%.

Based on the literature review presented above, table (2) is introduced to give an impression on the general trend in this research field. From Table (2), the following points must be taken into consideration:

- a. Lowest electrical efficiency achieved throughout this range was 4.7% while the highest was 18%. As for the thermal efficiency, the lowest and highest are 32.5% and 70%, respectively. The total PV/T efficiency ranges from 37.5% to 80%. It's important to note that 25%, 30% and 35% of researchers did not include PV-Thermal, and PV/T efficiency, respectively. The lack of presenting efficiency results is not recommended as it is an important parameter to be discussed.
- b. Highest efficiencies (both thermal and overall) were developed in Algeria, Tunisia, Malaysia, and China. Geographical location affects the amount of solar radiation, temperature, wind speed and other parameters.
- c. Most commonly used collectors are tube and sheet collectors, followed by CPC collectors. Air collectors were used more than water collectors throughout the review. As for the PV's Monocrystalline Silicon was used the most.
- d. The analytical method is used the most in this range with about 70% of researchers utilizing it, while the remaining followed numerical simulations. The lack of numerical and intuitive simulations must be addressed because it is vital to see the difference between the approaches for optimization or modeling. Using all methods and comparing their yield is recommended.

From the points illustrated above it is clear that there is a need for more numerical simulations and more extensive research targeting electrical efficiency as it is nowhere near the values produced for the thermal energy.

Table 2. PV/T Information from Literature Review

g	Authors	Location	Year	Method of study	Photovoltaic type	Thermal Collector /Absorber type	Efficiency (%)		
							Electrical	Thermal	PV/T
[1]	Sopian K. et al.	Malaysia	2013	Analytical	-	- Mono-facial - Bifacial Air based -Double/Single path	9-10	28-55	37 - 64
[2]	Fudholi A. et al.	Malaysia	2013	Analytical	-	Spiral flow absorber	13-13.8	45-55	58-68
[3]	Sopian K. et al.	Malaysia	2013	Analytical	-	-Serpentine flow absorber -Oscillatory flow absorber -Parallel-serpentine flow absorber	13	52	65
[4]	Staebler D. et al.	Croatia	2002	Analytical	Amorphous Silicon	Air based glass collector	4.7	32.5	37.5
[5]	Jian S. & Mingheng S.	China	2009	Numerical	-	Compound Trough Concentration	6-9.5	40 – 66	46-78
[6]	Touafek K.	Tunisia	2013	Analytical	Mono-	Tube and Sheet	14.4	-	-

	et al.				crystalline Si				
[7]	Ana Maria Croitoru	Bucharest	2013	-	-	-	-	-	-
[8]	Ammous M. and Chaabene M.	Tunisia	2014	Analytical	-	Glazed PVT Collector	18	68	75
[9]	Lv J. et al.	China	2013	Analytical and numerical	Mono-crystalline Si	Tube-Plate Collector	10.1	44.2	54.3
[10]	Hajji M. et al.	Morocco	2014	Analytical	Mono-crystalline Si	Tube and Sheet	-	-	-
[11]	Hadded S. et al.	Algeria	2015	Analytical	Mono-crystalline Si	Copper tubes	-	42	-
[12]	Athukoral A. et al.	Sri Lanka	2015	Analytical	Poly-crystalline Si	Water collector with glass tedler	14.55 – 14.95	49.9 – 54.8	64.3- 69.5
[13]	Khelifa A. et al.	Algeria	2014	Analytical	-	-Tube and Sheet -Serpentine flow	14.8	55	69
[14]	Ammous M. et al.	-	2016	Numerical	-	Tube and Sheet	-	-	-
[15]	Hajji M. et al.	Morocco	2014	Numerical	Mono-crystalline Si	-Tube and Sheet - Hybrid Water/Air	13.8 – 14	-	-
[16]	Reatti A. et al.	Italy	2015	Analytical	Mono-crystalline Si	Concentrating solar collector	-	-	-
[17]	Slimani M. et al.	Algeria	2015	Analytical & Numerical	Mono-crystalline	Air Collector	10	70	80
[18]	Marimuthu M. et al.	India	2015	Numerical	Transparent PV cell	Heat pipe array	-	-	42.7
[19]	Haber I.	Hungary	2015	Analytical	-	Heat pipe array	15	47	62
[20]	ChenHaiping et al.	China	2015	Numerical	-	Compound parabolic concentrator	7-11	50-52	60

B.2 PV Aspect of PV/T:

To examine the electrical aspect of the PV/T system, extensive review of papers focused on improving electrical efficiency or dealing with photovoltaics must be made.

As for the Photovoltaic system discussed in the literature, Table (3) is introduced to provide a clear idea about PV types, ranges and more. Table (3), illustrates a clearer and more distinct characteristics of the research that is conducted and can be summarized as follow:

- Most common size to PV modules is an open circuit voltage of 21 Volts and an average short circuit current of around 5.6 Amperes. As for the maximum output power, it ranges from [74 to 418] Watts, which shows small PV system.

- Monocrystalline silicon type PV the most commonly used type of PV modules in PV/T systems within this range of research.
- Type of configuration provided in the study is assumed to be stand-alone in case it was not mentioned. The majority of configurations used are stand-alone PV/T systems.
- Most authors did not discuss the economic point of view for PV/T.

The majority of the research works present in this sample accounts for small systems (below 418 Watts), with the stand-alone configuration of a mono-crystalline PV embedded with PV/T.

Table 3. PV Information from Literature Review

Ref.	Location	Type of PV used	Maximum Solar Radiation (W/m ²)	PV Open Circuit Voltage (V)	PV Short Circuit Current (A)	PV maximum output (W)	Type of PV configuration (Standalone) Or (Grid-Tie)	Cost of the PV system or energy (US\$)
[17]	Algeria	Mono-C	578	21.7	4.8	74.8	Stand-Alone	-
[18]	India	Transparent cell	351	21.6	3.8	418	Stand-Alone	-
[21]	-	Crystalline	-	-	-	-	Stand-Alone	-
[22]	Italy, Finland & Abu Dhabi	A-Si thin film	85	185	1.15	140	Stand-Alone	-
[23]	Egypt	A-Si thin film	-	71	2.5	110	Stand-Alone	-
[24]	Chile	Mono-C	560	21.7	4.8	75	Stand-Alone	-
[25]	Malaysia	Poly-C	-	21.5	2.53	40	Stand-Alone	-
[26]	China	Mono-C	616	45	5.56	-	Stand-Alone	-
[27]	Nigeria	Mono-C	172	45.9	9.16	315	Stand-Alone	-
[28]	Ireland	Poly & Mono- C	650	Poly (21.6)/ Mono (37.5)	Poly (2.51)/Mono (8.7)	Poly (40) / Mono (245)	Stand-Alone	-
[29]	Malaysia	Transparent	800	19.9	5.9	80	Stand-Alone	-
[30]	Slovenia	Mono-C	571	37.5	8.74	250	Stand-Alone	-
[31]	Spain	C-Si	-	22.2	9.46	-	Stand-Alone	-
[32]	Iran	Poly-C	800	21.1	3.8	-	Stand-Alone	-
[33]	China	Mono-C	768.5	45.1	5.63	195	Stand-Alone	-
[34]	Iran	-	220	44.53	4.967	-	Stand-Alone	-
[35]	Korea	Mono-C	-	38.1	9.27	260	Stand-Alone	412
[36]	France	Mono-C	598	-	-	250	Stand-Alone	-
[37]	India	C-Si & A-Si	-	-	-	-	Grid-Tied	-
[38]	India	Poly-C	240	37.1	8.28	230	Stand-Alone	208

C. Future work and Recommendations:

Even with the presented literature which covers a broad range of topics that are either core related to the PV/T or associated with it, there are some issues and ideas that need to be raised for further research. The recommendations are as follows:

1. Using various simulation methods then comparing them to find the optimized way to design PV/T.
2. Proposing ways to improve either the solar cell efficiency or the overall effectiveness other than the conventional ones.
3. Only employing solar cells of high quality and material characteristics in the PV/T system. All types of PV's must be analyzed experimentally with each type of collector present.
4. Providing economic studies and life cycle cost analysis for PV/T systems, which seems to be lacking in the literature?
5. Performing environmental analysis for the Green House Gases (GHG) emissions to the system to compare it to a rival non-renewable technology or a renewable one.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this paper presented review and study of research conducted by various scientists, researchers and experts in the field of PV/T collectors. Furthermore, it examined and presented their conclusions and recommendations. A classification of the PV/T technology was put in place, and a critical review was detailing the past, the present, and the future of R&D in this field. The primary significance of this paper was the critical review which helped in understanding the common grounds and the weak links in this area. The recommendations presented can be pursued to create future work to cover some of those shortcomings.

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